

(Re-)telling 12th century papal history

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Introduction

Medieval history, particularly diplomatics, have seen a peak in the publication of printed resources in the last decades of the 19th century.¹ These resources are known to be the most extensive overview of the documents issued during the medieval period, and they contain short summaries of medieval charters, called *regesta* documenting all relevant legal acts. The research presented in this paper is based on a project that investigates the disputed election of Pope Alexander III and the resulting schism during his mandate from 1159 till 1177.² Hence, a period that saw a culmination in issuing legal documents. The aim of the project can be divided into two tasks; the first task consists of an updated systematic overview of all textual witnesses from said period in a machine-accessible condition. The second aim is to use the encoded and annotated summaries (*regesta*) to re-assess the dynamics and processes that led to overcoming the schism between the opposing parties, namely the supporters of Pope Alexander III and those of the Holy Roman Emperor Frederick I Barbarossa. The act that sealed the reconciliation between the parties is today known and documented as the “Peace of Venice” in 1177. The presentation examines the development of a data model designed to enable a new, quantitative approach to analysing the information encoded in textual witnesses.

Background and Workflow

The corpus of the project consists of both retro-digitized print editions and databases with charters or *regesta* that are external to our project. The whole material—around 11,000 textual witnesses—will be made available digitally according to FAIR principles,³ in a format that adheres to research requirements of the 21st century and that allows large scale analysis. One major research output is a datamodel that allows to encode not only places, dates,

¹ The most prominent example is the Jaffé-Löwenfeld from 1888.

² The research presented in this paper is part of the project *Forming Europe by Overcoming Schism in the Twelfth Century*, funded by the Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities since 2023, for further information see: <https://formierung-europas.badw.de/>.

³ See Wilkinson et al. 2016.

organizations, and legal actors but also the juridical actions and mandates addressed in the documents. As a first step, we successfully established a workflow to transform the retro-digitized inventories of charters into structured data according to our XML based schema.⁴ The structure of those historic printed collections from the 19th century resembles already a database by following rigid rules and repeating structures. The metadata scheme applied is TEI XML based with an extension referring to the *Vocabulaire internationale de la diplomatique*⁵ to encode charter specific entities. Within the project we adapted the CEI2TEI datamodel by Vogeler and Winslow,⁶ that has been published as a proposal to insert concepts specific to charters to the TEI guidelines.⁷ XML files are known to be software independent and therefore expected to be sustainable, in addition they allow the project members to directly write and encode in XML. Relying on XML has also proven to be an advantage for mapping and transforming data from the printed inventories of issued charters as well as objects from further databases, e.g. *Regesta imperii*⁸ or *Papal Charters of the early and high Middle Ages*⁹. In addition, a TEI XML based datamodel is open to including further technologies for referencing and linking, such as RDF and other neighbouring standards for expressing formal languages. This becomes necessary as traditional encoding does not offer sufficient solutions to model information beyond legal actors, e.g. persons and organisations, places and dates that can be linked to new and existing authority files.¹⁰ In addition, we are also encoding the legal acts or events mentioned in each summary including their correlation to the schism.¹¹

Example: Encoding of *reference Points* in papal charters

While the encoding of the general structure of *regesta* is relatively straightforward, concerning the encoding of legal acts we encounter some intricacies that require creativity and new approaches. As example, in this presentation we focus on the document type “charter” and the connection to the events with relevance for the schism, with a focus on the

⁴ CEI2TEI Schema “Formierung Europas”, https://github.com/cceh/FormierungEuropas/blob/main/CEI_TEI_Schema/tei_cei_formierung_edited.rng.

⁵ See *Vocabulaire internationale de la diplomatique*, <https://www.cei.lmu.de/VID/>

⁶ Vogeler and Winslow, CEI2TEI, see <https://github.com/GVogeler/CEI2TEI>

⁷ <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/index.html>

⁸ *Regesta imperii*, see <https://www.regesta-imperii.de/>.

⁹ See <https://adw-goe.de/en/research/completed-research-projects/academies-programme/papal-charters/>.

¹⁰ We will refer to existing authority files where possible, like VIAF (<https://viaf.org/>), or the *People of Medieval Scotland-Database* (<https://poms.ac.uk/>) to mention two examples.

¹¹ See Fritze et al. 2021.

relationship between the issuer, recipients of the charters and Pope Alexander III, the main actor of the schism.

Example of a (historic) *regest*:

“Alexander III takes the collegiate chapter of Saint-Dié (Diocese of Toul) under papal protection, confirms its possessions, and grants it the free election of its provost. Rome, Lateran, 16 February 1179.” (JL 13290).¹²

Figure 1: Flow chart modelling the contents of a 'regest'.

The document summarised in this regest exhibits the characteristic tripartite structure of subject, predicate, and object. In the present case, Pope Alexander III instructs the collegiate church of Saint-Dié to undertake three specific actions. Assuming that the actions stipulated in such legal instruments are recurrent, they may be classified and associated with an authority file containing all attested actions referenced in the corpus of textual witnesses. In addition, we want to model and encode the point of reference between the action and the schism itself.

The aim of the present paper is therefore to present a proof of concept for the modelling of acts and their references to larger historic events. With our contribution at the conference, we

¹² Jaffé-Löwenfeld 1880: JL13290.

would like to discuss our findings and challenges with a broader community of experts in the domain of data driven studies in digital history.

References

Fritze, Christiane; Klug, Helmut W.; Kurz, Stephan 2021. *Datenmodell "eventSearch"*. In: KONDE Weißbuch. Hrsg. v. Helmut W. Klug unter Mitarbeit von Selina Galka und Elisabeth Steiner im HRSM Projekt "Kompetenznetzwerk Digitale Edition". Handle: hdl.handle.net/11471/562.50.53. PID: o:konde.53

Jaffé, Philipp, Wilhelm Wattenbach, Samuel Loewenfeld, Ferdinand Kaltenbrunner, and Paul Ewald. *Regesta pontificum romanorum: ab condita ecclesia ad annum post Christum natum MCXCVIII*. Lipsiae: Veit et comp., 1885.

Mark D. Wilkinson et al., 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship', *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1 (2016): 160018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.